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Research Article

PREVALENCE AND EPIDEMIOLOGICAL DESCRIPTION OF CLUBFOOT AT KING SAUD MEDICAL CITY RIYADH, SAUDI ARABIA

¹Dr. Jameel.H. Fakeeha, ²Dr. Abdullah Essa Alessa, ³Mohammed Hamad Alshathri,
⁴Musaad Salem Alkhaldi, ⁵Abdulaziz Nasser Althunayyan

¹Consultant Pediatric Orthopedic Surgery, jfakeeha@ksmc.med.sa

²Associate consultant orthopedic surgery, King Saud Medical City, alessa@ksmc.med.sa

³Medical Student, King Saud Bin Abdulaziz university, alshathrim@gmail.com.

⁴Medical Student, King Saud Bin Abdulaziz University, musaid22@gmail.com.

⁵Medical Student, King Saud Bin Abdulaziz University, althoniana@gmail.com.

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Abstract:

Objective: Clubfoot is a burden affecting 150,000 newborns every year. This study looks at the prevalence of clubfoot at King Saud Medical City (KSMC) and examine the risk factors associated with developing clubfoot in Saudi Arabia.

Data collection method: The data collected through the medical system (Medisys) and the database of the orthopedic department and obstetric and gynecology department at King Saud Medical City to determine the prevalence of club foot using the births recorded from 2015 to 2019 and reviewing their medical files to determine if they are affected by clubfoot. Additionally, the epidemiological description of Saudi clubfoot patients was attained by collecting a sample of 100 patients from the clubfoot clinic database for the patients following up from 2015 to 2019 at KSMC.

Results: A total of 18515 births at King Saud Medical City from 2015-2019 were evaluated and was found that 42 patients were affected by clubfoot resulting in a birth prevalence of 2.3 per 1000 (0.23%) among Saudis at KSMC. The epidemiological description of 100 patients seen in the clubfoot clinic at KSMC from Saudi Arabia resulted in finding that 48% of the cases affected bilaterally and 52% affected unilaterally and right foot 27%. And we found 2% of the cases have undescended testicle and 85% not associated with syndromes.

Conclusion: This study estimates the prevalence of clubfoot in Saudi Arabia to be 2.3/1000. Additionally, the findings support the data reported in the literature that males are more affected by clubfoot than females with twice the likelihood that males will be affected by clubfoot. Factors increasing the prevalence of clubfoot can be consanguineous marriages as seen in the Saudi population. This study will provide an initial look about club foot in Saudi Arabia which can build a base for future studies.

Key words: Clubfoot, congenital talipes equinovarus, talipes equinovarus, CTEV, TEV, epidemiology, prevalence, risk factors

Corresponding author:

Dr. Jameel .H. Fakeeha.,

Consultant Pediatric Orthopedic Surgery,

E-Mail: jfakeeha@ksmc.med.sa

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Congenital talipes equinovarus, also known as clubfoot, is considered one of the leading causes of congenital anomalies and disabilities in children.^{1, 2} Clubfoot can present alone or as a syndrome as part of other anomalies in which clubfoot becomes more difficult to treat.³ Some of the reported syndromes that can present with clubfoot as part of are spina bifida, arthrogryposis, or dystrophic dwarfism.⁴ Untreated clubfoot can cause functional disability and pain leading to children and families' suffering.⁵

There have been many of researches trying to identify the causes leading to congenital clubfoot and it was found that the most common cause is idiopathic.⁶ The variations in reported risk factors have been implied to be environmental such as maternal intrauterine variations,^{7, 8} and have also been reported to be genetics in multiple studies.^{9, 10} Male gender has been reported to be a risk factor for clubfoot in some studies.¹¹⁻¹³ A study looking at idiopathic clubfoot has found higher prevalence of clubfoot among firstborn.¹⁴ The variations in reported risk factors for clubfoot have been implied in most studies looking at the prevalence of clubfoot and the mechanisms of these factors leading to clubfoot are mostly unknown and a matter of debate.⁸⁻¹⁴

The reported incidence of clubfoot worldwide is about 1/1000 live birth with an estimated 150,000 children affected annually.¹⁵⁻²¹ There are a variety of studies looking at the prevalence of clubfoot in many countries around the world but none have been done in Saudi Arabia up to our knowledge. In this study, the prevalence of clubfoot in Saudi Arabia will be looked at by examining the reported cases at King Saud Medical City which is a tertiary hospital visited by many residents from all over Saudi Arabia. Also, this study will describe the population affected by clubfoot to better understand the risk factors leading to such condition as clubfoot is considered one of the leading causes of disabilities in children.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:**AIM OF THE STUDY:**

The research aims to assess the prevalence of clubfoot in King Saud Medical City, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia, and to describe the population that has been affected by clubfoot including family history and treatment method.

SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES:

- To assess the prevalence of club foot in King Saud Medical City, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia.
- Evaluate socio-demographical and medical factors of the patients with club foot.

- Generate a data of prevalence in King Saud Medical City for the cases of clubfoot that will help in future management of such cases.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The data was collected from patients' medical profiles through the medical system (Medisys) and the database of orthopedic department in King Saud Medical City.

STUDY AREA/SETTING:

The study was conducted at King Saud Medical City (KSMC). It is the biggest Ministry of Health tertiary hospital with capacities of 1500 beds. It was found in 1956 in Riyadh city. The orthopedic department is considered one of the outstanding departments at KSMC. It provides services to all age group in term of diagnosis, management, consultation, and preventing.

STUDY SUBJECTS:

The inclusion criteria for participation in this study will be Saudi patients with clubfoot diagnosis in both genders for the years 2015-2019. All details in Medical file and diagnosis should be fully clear and with all information about the patient. Age group of patients will be (0- 5) years.

INCLUSION CRITERIA:

- Saudi patients diagnosed with clubfoot.
- Age from 0 to 5 years.
- Both gender male and female.
- From 2015 to 2019.
- New or follow up patient.
- From all the country regions.
- Isolated disease or combined with other diseases.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

- Patients older than 5 years.
- Any patients not seen between 2015 to 2019.
- Non-Saudi patients.

STUDY DESIGN:

This is a retrospective descriptive cross-sectional study. This type of study was selected due to its analytical data abilities that meet the goal of this study.

STUDY POPULATION:

The study included all patients falling under the inclusion criteria. The population of birth at King Saud Medical City (KSMC) was used to calculate the birth prevalence of clubfoot.

SAMPLING TECHNIQUE:

Sampling will be through medical file review according to the list provided by database of

orthopedic department and the Medisys program of KSMC of patients following up in clubfoot clinic. Any Saudi patient meeting the inclusion criteria will be included.

DATA COLLECTION METHODS, INSTRUMENT USED, MEASUREMENTS:

After taking permission, the required data was collected throughout medical files including Saudi patients with clubfoot from Medisys and orthopedic database who are following up in clubfoot clinic in pediatric hospital at KSMC. The data was collected by highly qualified health care professionals whom they have enough experience and were supervised by two orthopedic physicians from KSMC.

DATA MANAGEMENT AND ANALYSIS PLAN:

Most of the analysis for this study was done to get frequency and percentage by using SPSS to analyse the data.

RESULTS:

A total of 18515 births at King Saud Medical City from 2015-2019 were evaluated and was found that 42 patients were affected by clubfoot resulting in a birth prevalence of 2.3 per 1000 (0.23%) among Saudis at KSMC.

The epidemiological description of clubfoot was attained from the orthopedics Department at King Saud Medical City by collecting data from 100 (N=100) cases that were following in the clinic for the years 2015-2019. Out of 100 patients, a total of 42 patients were born in KSMC with clubfoot. The characteristics of these cases outlined in Table 1 and Table 2. Result showed 68% of patients were male and 32% were female. Patients were born to 93% of mothers with no chronic illnesses, while 4% of mothers had asthma, 1% had Diabetes mellitus, and 2% had hypertension. There was no family history of clubfoot in 91% of the cases while 9% reported family history of clubfoot. It was found that 31% of the cases with clubfoot resulted from consanguineous marriage (identified as first or second cousins). There was 15% the of cases affected by developmental dysplasia of the hip. Clubfoot affected patients bilaterally in 48% and unilaterally in 52% of cases with the right foot affected in 27% and left foot affected in 25%.

As shown in the table 2, it was reported that 2% of the cases have asthma, 2% have speech difficulty and 2% have undescended testis and 1% has amblyopia, 1% has astigmatism, 1% has cardiac and hand anomaly, 1% has cystic fibrosis, 1% has diabetes mellitus, 1% has hydrocephalus, 1% has spinal bifida, 1% has spinal deformity, 1% has urinary incontinence while 85% has no associated syndromes or conditions.

Results also showed 12% of the patients following up in the clinic were waiting for surgery, 85% treated surgically in addition to serial casting, and 3% treated surgically and medical shoes as outlined in table 3.

Table 1: Characteristics seen in clubfoot cases collected from the orthopedics department at KSMC.

Characteristic	N=100
Gender	
Male	68
Female	32
Mother Chronic diseases	
Asthma	4
DM	1
HTN	2
None	93
Family history of clubfoot	
Yes	9
No	91
Consanguinity between parents	
Yes	31
No	69
Developmental Dysplasia of the hip (DDH)	
Yes	15
No	85
Clubfoot	
Bilateral	48
Unilateral	52
Right	27
Left	25

Table 2: Associated syndromes and medical conditions reported among patients.

Associated syndromes	N=100
Asthma	2
Amblyopia	1
Astigmatism, cardiac and hand anomalies	1
Cystic fibrosis	1
Diabetes Mellitus	1
Hydrocephalus	1
None	85
Speech difficulty	2
Spinal bifida	1
Spinal deformity	1
Undescended testis	2
Urinary incontinence	1

Table 3: Patients treatment status.

Treatment status	N=100
Follow up waiting for surgery	12
Surgery and serial casting	85
Surgery and medical shoes	3

DISCUSSION:

The data collected in this study found that the prevalence at KSMC is double that of the estimated prevalence of clubfoot worldwide; a prevalence of 2.3 per 1000 live birth at KSMC among Saudis. Worldwide, the reported prevalence of clubfoot is estimated to be 1/1000 live births.¹⁵⁻²¹ This can be attributed to factors such as the better screening and examinations postnatally and free healthcare for all Saudis. The higher prevalence found in this study can also be due to the consanguineous marriages seen in Saudi Arabia between cousins as seen in 31% of the cases that had parents that were relatives (First- or second-degree cousins) (Table 1). Studies from our part of the world where consanguinity marriages are common showed high prevalence of clubfoot.^{26, 27}

The study showed the male: female ratio was 2.1:1, which has been reported in many studies to be a risk factor with high incidence in male than female.¹¹⁻¹³

The study showed there is increase in incidence of speech difficulty, undescended testicles, and asthma with 2% incidence associated with clubfoot, which are important association clinically. There are reported

cases of undescended testicle associated with clubfoot in literature which support our findings.²⁸ Speech difficulties was reported in literature with neurodevelopmental difficulties associated with clubfoot.²⁹ Up to our knowledge there are no research associating asthma with clubfoot.

The reported prevalence of DDH in patients with clubfoot was found to be 4.1% in a systematic review and meta-analysis done in 2015 which is lower than the percentage seen in this study (15%)²⁴. Clubfoot has been associated with DDH in the literature and it was found that 15% of cases reported in this study were affected by clubfoot and DDH.²²⁻²⁴ This result can be due to the higher incidence of DDH found in Saudi Arabia that was reported in previous study as high as 3.8/1000 which is about four times the reported global incidence of DDH.²⁵ This study found no significant difference between the right or left foot in the unilaterally affected patients. There was no significant association between being affected by clubfoot and family history of clubfoot.

Some of the cases did not have surgery yet as of the end of 2019 and they were following up in the outpatient clinic for monitoring of the progression until the appointment of the surgery. The cases that received surgical intervention either continue using serial casting or medical shoes to prevent the tightness and shortening of the tendon. The cases who received surgical intervention and serial casting were the highest in treatment method; however, a small percentage of the cases were treated at another hospital initially then continued the treatment at KSMC.

CONCLUSION

It was found in this study that clubfoot affects 2.3 newborns out of 1000 live births. Factors increasing the prevalence of clubfoot can be consanguineous marriages seen in the Saudi population and better postnatal examination and follow-ups due to the free health care system in Saudi Arabia. This study supports the data reported in the literature that males are more affected by clubfoot than females with twice the likelihood that males will be affected by clubfoot. Also, this study found higher prevalence of DDH in patients with clubfoot. This study provides an initial look at the prevalence of clubfoot in Saudi Arabia by examining the reported cases at KSMC and future studies nationwide can give a better look at the prevalence of clubfoot in Saudi Arabia

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